

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

**BM-5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR
SEMESTER 1 2020/2021**

Reflective Critique Report

Lecturer: Pg Dr Siti Rozaidah Pg Hj Idris

Deadline: 22TH NOVEMBER 2020

**Hadiwansuaikalman Bin Haji Mohd Diah
20M1294**

Before experience

Before I am taking master of management my field is from social sciences majoring in professional communication and media and graduated in 2019. I do not know what to expect from taking a master's in management because I do not have any experience in the management field.

The reason I am taking a master's in management is because management skills are one of the important factors when we want to become a manager that will be in charge of the organization. In the working world a high percentage of employers indicated that because of the shortage of skill, they had issues with recruiting applicants with the right expertise and a lack of skilled staff in a given sector (Musa & Idris, 2020). Therefore it motivates me to pursue a master in management because of improving my skill in order to get a good job and a better future.

During experience

In this module we are given two assignments which are individual analysis and group work assignments and both of the assignments have different goals that need to be achieved when doing the task that was given by the lecturers. For the individual analysis I have decided to focus on the topic on motivation which is regarding identifying the motivation factor among students in learning for improving their academic performance. The step that has been undertaken for achieving the goal is by researching the topic on motivation in an academic journal and reading through about the topic and gaining a deeper knowledge about the topic. After I have done research on the topic on motivation factors among students I have identified the motivation factors which are intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, goal orientation, family encouragement and the role of educator. Then I make the report according to the journal article that has been reviewed and discuss what has been identified in the report.

While for the group assignment the topic we chose is regarding what had the educators, students and parents prepare towards online learning due to the Pandemic COVID-19. The project goals basically is about what action that had been taken by teachers, students and parents during the online learning because of temporary close down of school that was ordered by the government to stop the spread of the disease Pandemic COVID-19. At first the group work assignment we are supposed to make a case study. The step for our plan to achieve our goal for my group work assignment is that we had researched the journal article regarding the topic on the preparation of educators, students and parents about online learning because of pandemic COVID-19. Then we make a literature table that includes all article journals that we have reviewed. After that we have made an online questionnaire regarding our topic and distributed it to the participants. However due to unfortunate circumstances we have to remake our research and change our assignment into a systematic literature review due to the faculty cannot approve our primary research because of an unfavorable situation. After we gather all the information that is required to make the systematic literature review report. Then we make the report according to the theme that we have decided which are educators, students and parents.

The first aspect that I really learn in doing the project is getting feedback or review from the lecturer when we plan something on doing the project just to make sure that we are on the right track or we can get advice on how to improve our research. The second aspect that I learn when doing the project is that we have to think carefully regarding the decision that we are going to make because it can significantly affect the result at the end of the project. Behavioural theory of decision-making defined the making of optimal choices is constrained by minimal rationality (Buchanan & Huczynski, 2010). When we make the decision we have to consider the personality, relationship with the group, external environment and based on the information that has been collected. In order the decision that we made can gain the most benefit from it.

For the individual project the things that I do is research regarding the topic that I already choose which is about motivation. From my opinion the individual analysis project that I chose is quite a very interesting topic to be research on because by identifying the motivation factors we know what factors that increase students motivation to learn is their study. However there is some challenges that I face during making the individual analysis which is finding the relevant article journal regarding the topic about motivation factors among students is quite difficult that it is one the most time-consuming part of the task when doing the individual analysis because there a lot of research regarding motivation in the academic resources but there are only a few articles journals that meet the criteria about the topic motivation among students and some of the articles journals cannot be access because the journal article need to be paid in order to access it. Therefore I have to do more research regarding the topic motivations among students from a few academic journals database websites to find the specific topic that meets my research. After all the required information has been found then I divided the data into different themes that have the same content and next in the start to make the individual analysis report which contains the introduction, methodology, findings, discussion and conclusions.

While for the group project which is regarding the preparation of educators, students and parents about online learning due to pandemic COVID-19 so our group have to research regarding the challenges and solutions that were made during the online learning due to pandemic COVID-19. For the report there are some task that need be done by each member for every part of the report such as for the theoretical framework every member have to find a theory that is relevant for our topic which the theory that I had identified is contingency theory which is about when making a decision in a situation, it involves the leader in order to monitor and enhance the feasibility of a strategy of choice (Goodnow, 1982) . However there is some part of the report that is in charge by each member of the group and I am in charge of writing the conclusion part of the group report and checking the references of the report to make sure that the references are all included and it is in the correct order .

While for the other group member they also have a contribute for each part of the report such as each one group member have to find articles journal that are related to our topics and also each member of the a specific task that there need to in charge that each one of the member will focus on either on educators, students or parents.

Due to the unfortunate circumstances we have to change our type of report from a case study to a systematic literature review where we only allowed to use secondary data for our group assignment and one of our member suggests that to include more aspects instead of one aspect because initially the task only focus only on educator and this may result lack of content that will be discussed in our paper. Therefore we agree to include more aspects that will be included in our report to make our study can analyse more aspects that can impact during pandemic COVID-19 which make agreement to analyse aspects in terms of educators, students and parents in online learning during pandemic COVID-19.

Completion of experience

The outcome from my individual assignment is that I am able to identify the motivation factors among students that can benefit the education system for improving the student motivation which increases the probability of academic performance of the student. While for the group work assignment we had to identify what are the challenges and solutions for the group work regarding the preparedness of Educators, students and parents about online learning because of pandemic COVID-19.

The personal strengths that I can identify are being able to help and improve the reports to make sure that the work is done correctly and while my weaknesses are that my time management skill is not really efficient, that it can affect my work flow of the project to become more stressful. The professional development from the project is to be more organised when doing the research workflow in order to manage time more efficiently.

There are two things that I would do differently next time when doing projects which is to start early so that I can organise and plan what should be done to future projects and improve my time management skill and secondly is to get a feedback or review from my lecturer in order to know what we are doing are at the right track or to get an advice or guidance to improve our quality of reports in case the plan we make need to be corrected. With the reflective report I can critically analyse my personal strengths and weaknesses and learn what should be improved for increasing self development skill.

References

- Buchanan, D., & Huczynski, A. (2010). *Organizational behaviour* (7th ed., p. 632). Harlow: Prentice Hall/Financial Times.
- Goodnow, W. (1982). The Contingency Theory of Education. *International Journal Of Lifelong Education*, 1(4), 341-352. doi: 10.1080/0260137820010404
- Musa, S. F., & Idris, D. S. (2020). Addressing Issues of Unemployment in Brunei: The Mismatch Between Employers Expectations and Employees Aspirations. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management (IJABIM)*, 11(2), 88-101. doi:10.4018/IJABIM.2020040106